

1 **Unique and overlapping contributions of interferon gamma and muramyl dipeptide to activation of**
2 **antigen presentation by MHC class I and II genes.**

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7 NOD2, the muramyl dipeptide sensor of the innate immune system, controls expression of a select group
8 of receptors encoded by class I and class II MHC genes. Muramyl dipeptide signaling in human cells also
9 results in transactivation of class I and class II histocompatibility genes, and this is separable from NOD2
10 control of MHC-I and MHC-II family genes. Interferon gamma controls composite antigen presentation
11 potential by supporting Th2 CD4+ helper T-cell differentiation and activating expression of CIITA, the class
12 II transcriptional activator. Here we measured total transcription in human monocytes following exposure
13 to muramyl dipeptide, to interferon gamma or both which demonstrate unique but overlapping
14 contributions of a cytokine with largely antiviral origin that functions in hematopoiesis and a molecular
15 pattern recognized as non-self in shaping the MHC-I/MHC-II repertoire of immune cells.

16 **References**

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